

Development of an efficient logging system using the LOGGFORCAT boom harvester

Introduction

LOGGFORCAT is an operational project that has created an innovative wood clearing system based on the construction of a prototype 15-meter telescopic arm with a fastener that allows easier track-side clearance of felled trees, stacking them to match forest truck loading requirements, improving yields, reducing environmental impact and improving safety in forestry work. Description of the actions carried out in the project:

- Design and construction of the LOGGFORCAT RS prototype.
- Design and validation of clearing system with the LOGGFORCAT RS prototype.
- Pilot tests for the validation of the LOGGFORCAT RS prototype and LOGGFORCAT clearing system.
- Transfer of results.

Lessons learned

Description of the actions carried out in the project. Design and construction of the LOGGFORCAT RS prototype. Design and validation of clearing system with the LOGGFORCAT RS prototype. Pilot tests for the validation of the LOGGFORCAT RS prototype and LOGGFORCAT clearing system. Transfer of results The prototype, LOGGFORCAT RS, has been created, involving a collection arm with clamp, which is approved and bears the CE mark. The prototype allows clearing with a new, more financially and environmentally efficient system.

For further information contact

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The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://singularwood.cat/>

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